

Interlaminar Strength Improvement for CFRP Laminates by Zanchor Technology

Yutaka Iwahori¹, Ken Yamada², Masayasu Ishibashi³, Fumihito Takeda⁴,
Yosuke Nagao¹, Takashi Ishikawa¹ and Goichi Ben²

1 Advanced Composite Evaluation Technology Center, Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency

2 College of Industrial Technology, Nihon University

3 Central research laboratory, Shikibo Ltd.

4 Nagoya Aerospace Systems Works, Mitsubishi Heavy Industries Ltd.

KEYWORDS: Zanchor, CAI, interlaminar strength, impact damage

1 INTRODUCTION

Improvement in interlaminar strength for CFRP laminates was experimentally evaluated by using a new material technology called “Zanchor”. The Zanchor technology is one of the interlaminar strength improvement methods by using through-the-thickness fibers[1]. Schematic view of the Zanchor process is shown in Fig.1. Some kind of special needle is stuck repeatedly into the non-crimp dry prepfom perpendicularly. Several inter-layers of non-crimp fabric (NCF) fibers are entangled by special needle. This process is entangled in-plane fibers to the other layers by the special needle. After the process, the dry preform is impregnated and cured by resin film infusion. These entangled fibers in the CFRP laminates may affect interlaminar strength improvement such as interlaminar fracture toughness, and peel strength. It is also expected that compression after impact (CAI) strength which governed by interlaminar strength properties of CFRP laminates is improved.

In this report, mechanical properties of the Zanchor CFRP laminates were obtained, including tension, compression, open hole compression, impact delamination size and CAI strength for several densities of Zanchor. Moreover DCB test for CFRP laminates were also carried out for several densities of Zanchor. Mode I crack energy release rate (G_{IR}) of Zanchor CFRP laminates were obtained by DCB test data.

Fig. 1 Schematic of the Zanchor process

2 TEST SPECIMENS

A summary of test matrix is listed in Table 1. Several Zanchor densities of CFRP laminates are prepared Zanchor-0 to -4 for every type of test specimens. Zanchor-0 is non Zanchor as control. The following suffix "-x" of "Zanchor" indicates multiple number of density of Zanchor which compared with Zanchor-1. For example, Zanchor-4 has 4 times of Zanchor-1 in density. There are three types of ply orientations. Type A is [45/0/-45/90]_s quasi-isotropic laminates, type B is [45/0/-45/0/90/-45/0/45]_s, and type C is [0/90/90/0]_{2s} for DCB tests. The non-crimp fabric fiber is a high strength grade and resin is a 180 degree cured type for RTM. CAI strength test was carried out for two impact energy cases. Table .2 shows the summary of test matrix for impact energy conditions of CAI tests.

Table 1. Summary of test matrix

Type of test specimen	Type	Ply orientation	Zanchor density			
			0 (Non Zanchor)	1	2	4
Non hole tension	A	[45/0/-45/90] _s			3	
	B	[45/0/-45/0/90/-45/0/45]			3	
Non hole compression	A	[45/0/-45/90] _{s2}	3	4	4	4
	B	[45/0/-45/0/90/-45/0/45] _s	3	4	4	4
Open hole compression	A	[45/0/-45/90] _{s2}	3	4	4	4
	B	[45/0/-45/0/90/-45/0/45] _s	3	4	4	4
Compression after impact	A	[45/0/-45/90] _{s2}	3 (See detail for table 2)			
	B	[45/0/-45/0/90/-45/0/45] _s				
DCB	C	[0/90/90/0] _{2s}			5	

Table 2 Summary of test matrix for impact energy conditions of CAI tests.

	TypeA : [(45/0/-45/90) _{sym}] ₂		TypeB : [45/0/-45/0/90/-45/0/45] _{sym}	
	Impact Energy (J/mm)		Impact Energy (J/mm)	
	3.3	6.7	3.3	6.7
Zanchor-0	1	2	1	2
Zanchor-1	1	2	1	2
Zanchor-2	1	2	1	2
Zanchor-4	1	2	1	2

The number of specimens

3 EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

3.1 Tensile strength tests

Several densities of Zanchor CFRP laminates were tested static tensile strengths and modulus in an Instron 8502 hydraulic testing machine. The crosshead speed was chosen as 1.0 mm/min and strain gages were used on the both sides for strain measurements. A picture of a tensile test set is shown in Fig.2. Figure 3 shows the averaged test results of tensile strength and modulus of three data for all types of Zanchor. Modulus of type A and B were almost constant values when density of Zanchor increased. On the other hand, deterioration of tensile

strength was observed when density of Zanchor increased. Zanchor-4 of type A was lower strength than Zanchor-0 by about 12%. It was suggested that increasing of Zanchor makes damages of in-plane fibers of the preform then tensile strength was deteriorated.

Fig. 2 Tensile test set

Fig. 3 Tensile test results

3.2 Compressive strength tests

Static compressive strength and modulus of Zanchor CFRP were measured an Instron 8502 hydraulic testing machine with the inter-grip distance of 25.0 mm. The crosshead speed was chosen as 0.5 mm/min and strain gages were used on the both sides for strain measurements. These compressive test specimens were cramped directly by the grip of crosshead. A picture of a fractured compressive test specimen is shown in Fig.4. All test specimens were fractured by compression mode. Figure 5 shows the averaged test results of compressive strength and modulus of three data for all types of Zanchor CFRP. Modulus of type A was almost constant values when density of Zanchor increased. Type A strength was also constant even in Zanchor density increased. On the other hand, type B results were scattered not only modulus but also strength. It was found that deterioration of compressive modulus and strength of type B were observed in Zanchor-4. Type B Zanchor-4 strength was lower than Zanchor-0 by about 12%. It was observed that increasing density of Zanchor for type A, quasi-isotropic laminates, did not so affect to the compressive strength. However type B modulus and strength deterioration were observed on Zanchor-4.

Fig. 4 Fractured compressive test specimen

Fig. 5 Compressive test results

3.3 Open hole compression test

Open hole compression strengths of various densities of Zanchor CFRP were tested on an Instron 4482 screw driven testing machine with platen plates. The speed of crosshead was set to 0.5 mm/min. This compressive test specimen and loading fixture were used NAL-III method which was developed by JAXA (former NAL) as targeting for efficiency and cost reduction of OHC test method. The NAL-III loading fixture has the same window size as SACMA standard. The test specimen width and open hole diameter size are also the same as the SACMA test specimen, 38.1 mm and 6.35 mm respectively. The NAL-III test specimen length is 118 mm which is smaller than SACMA specimen. Figure 6 shows the OHC test set of NAL-III method. Figure 7 shows the averaged test results of OHC strength of three data for all types of Zanchor CFRP. It was found that OHC strength was not affected so much by difference of Zanchor densities.

Fig. 6 OHC test set of NAL-III method

Fig. 7 OHC test results

3.4 Compression after impact test [2]

3.4.1 Impact test

Impact test was carried out for Zanchor CFRP before compression strength test according to SACMA SRM 2R-94 standard. Impact test was employed an Instron 9250HV drop weight type low speed impact machine. The drop weight is 5.07 kg with 9.53 mm (3/8") diameter striker head. Before and after impact tests, ultrasonic C-scan was carried out. Impact energies were 6.7 J/mm and 3.35 J/mm.

Ultrasonic C-scanning results after impact tests are shown in Figure 8(a) to (d) as impact energy condition 6.7 J/mm type B. These C-scanning images scanned from the impact side. In Zanchor-0 and Zanchor-4, each result was an extremely different from delamination size. Especially, large delamination area was expanded to the half of the test specimen on Zanchor-0. Furthermore, B-scope images are shown in these figures that an abacus shape of delamination which the maximum delamination length was appeared near the half of the lamniate thickness was observed. Figure 9 shows the result of impact delamination areas for different densities of Zanchor type A and B. The delamination areas of Zanchor-0, both type A and B, decreased of over 60% compared with Zanchor-0. It was confirmed that deterrent capability of delamination propagation for CFRP laminates is improved by the Zanchor technology.

Fig.8 Ultrasonic C-scanning images for after impact (Impact energy: 6.7J/mm, Type B).

Fig.9 Delamination areas after impact for several densities of Zanchor

3.4.2 CAI strength

CAI strengths were measured by an Instron 4250 screw driven testing machine. A picture of the CAI test set is shown in Fig.10. The relationships between CAI strengths and densities of Zanchor for impact energy 6.7 J/mm are shown in Fig.11. CAI strengths were increase with increasing density of Zanchor both type A and B. Especially, Zanchor-4 of type A improved 66% compared with Zanchor-0. The CAI strength of Zanchor-4 Type B also improved 42%. On the other hand, in the higher densities of Zanchor CFRP for type B, Zanchor-2 and -4, it seems that CAI strengths were reached the limit. It was suggested that increasing Zanchor density was improved CAI strength of the CFRP laminates, but there was a limit in improvement of CAI strength of the Zanchor CFRP laminates.

Fig. 10 A picture of CAI test set

Fig. 11 CAI strength test results (6.7 J/mm)

3.5 DCB (double cantilever beam) test

DCB tests for several densities of Zanchor CFRP laminates were carried out. Mode I energy release rates (G_{IR}) were calculated from load-COD (crack opening displacement) curves and crack lengths by using area method. Insert tongue type of DCB test fixture was employed here. Figure 12 shows a DCB test set with AE sensor. Figure 13 shows load-COD curves and crack propagation curves for several Zanchor densities. In this figure, the maximum load of Zanchor-0 to -4, Zanchor-4 is 2.5 times as higher as Zanchor-0. The load-COD curves are also shifted upward, so that density of Zanchor increase. Moreover delamination propagations are postponed when density of Zanchor increase. This is a crack propagation deterrent effect for CFRP laminates by Zanchor technology. DCB test data reduction results were shown

Fig.12 Zanchor DCB test set

Table 3 DCB test results

Number of Zanchor	G_{IR}
Zanchor-0	0.67
Zanchor-1	1.14
Zanchor-2	1.62
Zanchor-4	2.10

in table 3. The relationships between density of Zanchor and averaged G_{IR} were plotted in Fig 14 with linear regression curves for Zanchor plots. The value of G_{IR} tends to increase as the densities of Zanchor increases. The relationship between G_{IR} and density of Zanchor is almost linear between Zanchor-0 and -2. It seems that increase density of Zanchor was improved G_{IR} of the CFRP laminates almost linearly. However, there is a value of Zanchor-4 G_{IR} under the regression curve by about 18 %. It is suggested that the relation of the G_{IR} -Zanchor density is no longer linear, when some value of the density of Zanchor is exceeded.

Fig.13 Load-COD curves and crack length

Fig.14 G_{IR} and Zanchor density

4 DISCUSSION

Mechanical properties of Zanchor CFRP laminates were measured. As a result, it was observed that some tension and compression properties were deteriorated by increasing of the Zanchor density. On the other hand, it was cleared from DCB tests that the interlaminar strength of CFRP (G_{IR}) is improved. Moreover prevention of low-speed impact delamination propagation property and subsequent compression after impact strengths also improved. A picture of sectional cut view of Zanchor CFRP laminates is shown in Fig. 15. It is observed that some carbon fibers entered between other layers, at the same time some in-plane fibers are damaged. It is suspected that the damage of these fibers is caused by Zanchor when special needles repeatedly stuck to the preform. And the damage of in-plane fibers make a deterioration of mechanical properties of CFRP laminates such as tensile strength and compressive strength type B. On the other hand, in a manufacturing process, it is known that the Zanchor is effective in the improvement of permeability for the thick preform. It must be considered that the effect of both in-plane and out of plane mechanical properties, and manufacturing requirements are satisfied.

Fig.15 A picture of microscope for Zanchor CFRP section cut

Moreover it is necessary to study more detail mechanism of interlaminar strength improvement, effect of in-plane mechanical properties, and also permeability of the preform by Zanchor technology further hereafter.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Improvement in interlaminar strength for CFRP laminates was experimentally evaluated by using a new material technology Zanchor. The following findings are unveiled through the experiments.

1. Tensile strength may affect Zanchor density. Deterioration of tensile strength was observed when density of Zanchor increased. Zanchor-4 of type A was lower strength than Zanchor-0 by about 12%.
2. Quasi-isotropic laminates, type A, did not so affect to the compressive strength when Zanchor density increased. However type B modulus and strength deterioration were observed on Zanchor-4.
3. OHC strength did not affect density of Zanchor in this test results.
4. Delamination area of Zanchor-4 after impact decreased over 60% compared with Zanchor-0. It was confirmed that the delamination propagation deterrent capability was improved by the Zanchor technology.
5. CAI strengths were improved by increasing density of Zanchor. However, CAI strength of Zanchor-4 was already reached the maximum strength because of CAI strengths are not improved in Zanchor-2 to -4.
6. Mode I interlaminar energy release rate of G_{IR} for CFRP laminates was improved by increasing of Zanchor density. The relationship between Zanchor density and G_{IR} values from this DCB test result was almost linear. However it was observed a trend in high Zanchor density that G_{IR} was the limit of improvement.
7. It must be considered that the Zanchor effects of both in-plane and out of plane mechanical properties.

6 ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to express gratitude to Mr. Fujishima, Mr. Yamazaki and Mr. Ichikawa in Ishikawajima Jet Service Co., Ltd who supported many test, and Mr. Tetsuji Kato, and Mr. Taichi Itabashi who carried out tensile test and DCB test.

7 REFERENCES

- 1] T. Abe, K. Hayashi, T. Sato, S. Yamane, T. Hirokawa: "A-VaRTM process and Zanchor technology for primary aircraft structures", *Proc. of SAMPE Europe, 2003*, pp.87-95.
- 2] K. Yamada, Y. Iwahori, M. Ishibashi, T. Fukuoka, T. Ishikawa and G. Ben: "Compression-After-Impact Characteristics of Zanchor CFRP Laminates", *Proc. of US-JAPAN 2004*.